

DISPOSAL AND RECYCLING OF POLYETHYLENE**Abdullayeva I.***Candidate of Chemical Sciences, senior lecturer of the
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Nuriyev A.***Master degree of the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Abstract**

The recycling and disposal of polymers as waste are rapidly developing. Therefore, the emergence of new equipment and the improvement of technologies are essential. The essence of the process, the possible types of products obtained, and the development prospects of this field are constantly being reviewed. More than 40% of the produced plastics are used in packaging, with 47% of them being allocated for food packaging. Due to their low cost, high aesthetic appearance, convenience, and safety, they are used in the production of packaging products suitable for specific conditions. However, 40% of such synthetic polymer packaging products become household waste that never decomposes. Annually, the amount of household waste per person reaches 40-50 kg. Nevertheless, the relevance of the polymer waste recycling problem is not only related to environmental protection but also to the transformation of plastic waste into a valuable raw material and energy resource in conditions of polymer raw material shortages.

Keywords: Polyethylene waste, plastic recycling, microplastics, marble dust as filler, polyethylene composites, marble powder reinforced polyethylene, modification with filler.

Recent research results have raised increasing concerns. It has been discovered that microplastic particles are present in the fetus, surrounding the baby in the womb. It is assumed that microplastics enter the mother's placenta through food, drink, or inhalation. These particles have been found on both the maternal and fetal sides of the placenta, as well as within the membrane where the fetus develops. The fact that the detected microplastics were of various colors (blue, red, orange, or pink) suggests that they originate from packaging, cosmetics, paint, and personal care products. Experts in this field warn that these particles can have long-term harmful effects on the human body and negatively impact the developing immune system of the fetus. Since each microplastic particle measures about 10 microns (0.01 mm), they can easily enter the bloodstream and be transported throughout the body. Recent research conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO) has concluded that adults ingest 300-600 microplastic particles per day. Professor John Boland from Dublin University, noting that most of these particles are expelled from the body, emphasizes the need for further research to determine how many of them mix with the bloodstream and affect other organs.

Research has shown that as temperature increases, more microplastics dissolve into water. However, the impact of microplastic consumption on human health remains unknown. Prof. Boland states: "We do not yet know whether exposure to microplastics has any negative effects on our health." For these reasons, reducing polyethylene production and recycling its waste products are among the critical issues of the day, as they contribute to maintaining the balance of the ecosystem [1-2].

In recent years, the increasing use of polymer materials has made the disposal of used materials a serious problem. Since polyethylene is one of the most widely used polymers in various fields, it constitutes a significant portion of total thermoplastic waste. Therefore, the

recycling process of polyethylene requires further research. In this study, the mechanical properties of polyethylene (HDPE) were experimentally investigated to determine the effect of the proportion of recycled material in a primary and recycled/primary polyethylene blend on tensile strength, impact viscosity, and fluidity. The results showed that after three cycles of HDPE recycling, density, elastic modulus, relative elongation, impact viscosity, and elastic deformation decreased, while the tensile strength limit increased. As the ratio of recycled polyethylene to virgin HDPE increased, density, impact viscosity, and recovery rate improved, while flexural modulus, elongation percentage, and tensile strength at break remained nearly constant. Recycling helps protect the soil, as landfills fill up quickly, and finding suitable locations becomes increasingly difficult due to noise and odor complaints from nearby residents. The primary way to reduce the need for new landfill sites is to recycle waste. Additionally, recycling products generate less pollution compared to producing new ones, thereby reducing pollution-related diseases. From an economic perspective, recycling reduces the demand for raw materials and saves energy. The growing interest in plastic recycling is driven by three major trends:

1. The increase in plastic production and consumption.
2. The sharp rise in polymer prices.
3. Stricter disposal regulations due to growing environmental concerns.

Certain factors can negatively affect the quality of recycled plastic, including possible degradation during its service life and the introduction of foreign materials during recycling. However, the primary challenge remains the sorting of different types of plastics. Polyethylene is the most widely used plastic material. Its leading position is mainly due to its low cost and important industrial properties, such as high strength at room temperature, sufficient toughness at low temperatures, high elasticity across a wide temperature range (even down to -73°C), high corrosion resistance, and the absence of

odor and taste. Thus, HDPE is widely used in the production of containers, pipes, electrical insulation, chemical tubing, household items, and blow-molded bottles. Recently, new application areas have emerged, including cement dust plants, drainage systems, petrochemical plants, municipal pipelines, and swimming pools. Recycled HDPE can be used in various products, such as soft drink bottles, flower pots, wastewater pipes, stadium seats, partitions for golf bags, detergent bottles, and toys. The aim of this experimental study is to examine the mechanical properties of virgin HDPE under normal conditions, including elastic modulus, yield strength, relative elongation, impact viscosity according to the Charpy test, fluidity, recovery rate, density, and the effect of the percentage of recycled material [3-4].

The use of polymer waste allows for significant savings in primary raw materials (primarily oil) and electricity.

Plastic waste can be divided into three groups:

a) Technological production waste generated during the synthesis and processing of thermoplastics. These waste materials are processed into various products, used as additives to raw materials, etc.;

b) Industrial waste, which accumulates due to the failure of polymer products. These wastes are less contaminated and homogeneous, making their recycling easier;

c) Municipal waste, which is collected from public catering establishments and households. These wastes are disposed of in city landfills, where they mix with other waste, forming complex waste mixtures. Recycling such mixed waste is difficult because the thermoplastics in household waste are incompatible and require separation at different stages. Additionally, collecting obsolete polymer products from the population is an extremely complex organizational task, which has not yet been fully established in our country. Most waste is disposed of by landfilling or incineration. However, waste disposal is neither economically viable nor technically easy. Moreover, burying and burning polymer waste contributes to soil and environmental pollution. The incomplete combustion of polymer products results in soot formation and the release of toxic gases, which further pollutes the air and water. Additionally, due to severe corrosion, incinerators quickly become inoperable. In the 1970s, intensive research began on the development of biodegradable, photodegradable, and water-soluble polymers. The production of biodegradable polymers caused a sensation and was initially considered the ideal method for eliminating plastic waste. However, subsequent studies revealed that combining high physical and mechanical properties, aesthetic appearance, rapid degradation, and low cost in one product is challenging. The primary method of utilizing plastic waste is recycling, i.e., reusing it. Research has shown that the main disposal methods are economically viable, with operating costs not exceeding and, in some cases, even being lower than waste destruction costs. Another advantage of recycling is that it produces additional useful products for various industries without re-polluting the environ-

ment. For these reasons, recycling is not only economically but also environmentally beneficial. It has been estimated that only a small portion (a few percent) of polymer waste generated from outdated products is recycled annually. The main obstacles include difficulties in initial waste processing (collection, sorting, separation, cleaning, etc.) and the lack of specialized equipment for processing. Main Methods of Plastic Waste Recycling:

1. Thermal decomposition by pyrolysis
2. Decomposition to obtain low-molecular-weight products (monomers, oligomers)
3. Mechanical recycling

Pyrolysis is the thermal decomposition of organic materials with or without oxygen. The pyrolysis of polymer waste allows for the production of high-calorific fuel, raw materials, and semi-finished products used in various technological processes, as well as monomers for polymer synthesis. Many polymers can be broken down into their original components through reverse reactions. The decomposition methods for PET, polyamides, and foamed polyurethanes are particularly important for practical applications. The resulting decomposition products can be used as raw materials for polycondensation processes or as additives to primary materials. However, contaminants present in these products often make it impossible to produce high-quality polymer fibers, though their purity is sufficient for producing casting compounds, quick-melting adhesives, and soluble adhesives. The most common method of waste processing is still thermal treatment, which is highly cost-effective. Currently, mechanical recycling of polymer waste into secondary materials is the most practical method. This approach does not require expensive specialized equipment and can be implemented in any location where waste is collected [5-10].

Polyethylene (PE) is a polymer distinguished by its density and other characteristics. Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) is produced under high pressure, making it soft. It has a melting temperature of 103-110 °C, is resistant to aggressive environments, and can be colored. It is used in laminates, stretch films, and coatings. High-density polyethylene (HDPE) is harder than LDPE. At 20-22 °C, up to 80% crystallinity is achieved, and it melts at 125-132 °C. It is used for chemical-resistant containers for acids and other reagents. Medium-density polyethylene (MDPE) is a blend that combines the advantages of LDPE and HDPE and is used for thick-walled materials. PE is widely used due to its versatility and low cost. Common applications include coatings, disposable containers, food packaging, children's toys, insulation materials, medical devices (prosthetics, surgical instruments), transportation (shock-absorbing materials for pipelines, mechanical protection), and electrical device casings. Despite its benefits, PE poses serious environmental and health hazards. It contains toxic heavy metals, mainly lead. Cold storage of PE food wraps can release toxins, increasing product acidity. High temperatures cause PE to release formaldehyde, a strong carcinogen. The widespread use of PE has improved human welfare, but its long-term environmental impact requires urgent at-

tention. Sustainable solutions such as recycling, reducing production, and developing biodegradable alternatives are essential for minimizing these risks [11-12].

The differences in the properties of these materials are influenced by various factors. Aging and oxidation lead to primary degradation, causing chemical changes such as the formation of carbonyl groups, hydroperoxides, and double bonds, as well as the development of excited centers for further oxidation. These processes also result in changes in molecular weight due to degradation, branching, and cross-linking, ultimately affecting the rheology of melts and the mechanical properties of the material. Scientific and technical analyses indicate that nearly all thermoplastics can be recycled by introducing carefully selected additives that slow down degradation. It is crucial to determine in advance which type of product the recycled raw material will be used for. By incorporating chemical modifiers, it is possible to significantly increase or decrease the processability of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) regranelates. For example, the processability of regranelates (from canisters and bottles) can be modified using MB-1 additives (bismaleimide derivatives), which influence the viscosity and physical-mechanical properties of the composition. Notably, a decrease in processability is accompanied by a significant increase in the elasticity of the composition, while its strength properties remain unchanged. The addition of unsaturated elastomers makes the melt more elastic and increases processability, but it does not significantly affect the strength characteristics of the regranelate [13-14].

When fillers are added to used polyethylene (PE), various functional groups form on the surface of the fillers, interacting with the polymer matrix. These functional groups enhance interfacial adhesion, filler dispersion, and the overall mechanical and thermal properties of the composite. The most commonly used fillers include stone powder, calcium carbonate (marble powder), and other industrial waste materials. Due to their surface reactivity, these fillers undergo certain chemical reactions, leading to the formation of functional groups. The addition of waste fillers such as marble powder and stone powder provides a sustainable and cost-effective method for improving the mechanical, thermal, and physical properties of polyethylene. These fillers, derived from industrial or natural byproducts, not only reduce material costs but also contribute to environmental sustainability. When incorporated into polyethylene, specific functional groups are introduced through surface modifications or compatibilizers. These functional groups enhance interfacial adhesion between the filler and the polymer matrix, leading to improved composite performance. Marble powder, which mainly consists of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), is a rich byproduct of the marble industry. Calcium carbonate naturally contains hydroxyl (-OH) groups on its surface. These groups react with fatty acids, such as stearic acid, forming carboxyl (-COOH) groups. This modification allows calcium carbonate to adhere more effectively to the polymer, improving its compatibility with the matrix. The resulting carboxyl groups form chemical bonds with the polyethylene matrix, increasing mechanical strength and enhancing the

material's tear resistance. The structural and property changes of thin films made from low-density polyethylene (LDPE) under various natural climatic conditions and over time have been studied, along with potential modifications to restore lost properties. The optimal amounts of mineral fillers—20-25 parts per hundred (phr) of seashell limestone, 6-8 phr of sludge, and zeolite—were found to help restore some lost properties of used polyethylene greenhouse covers in the “Central Aran” region and the Absheron Peninsula. However, it was shown that mineral fillers alone do not allow for the production of highly filled composites from used polyethylene. The optimal amounts of sludge, zeolite, and seashell fillers slightly improve the mechanical durability of used polyethylene, but they are insufficient for comprehensive property restoration. These findings are attributed to the fact that used LDPE, unlike virgin LDPE, contains 25.0-28.6% of an insoluble fraction and has become a brittle material with reduced elasticity. It has been demonstrated that structural and property modifications of used LDPE during recycling are only possible when combined with low molecular weight functional oligomers—such as ED-20, MFFO + ED-16—and polypropylene derivatives containing chlorine, sulfochlorinated groups, dispersants, and phase compatibilizers like SKEPT-60. Further studies show that at the polymer-polymer and filler-polymer phase separation boundaries, the use of modifying, dispersing, and compatibilizing polymers allows for the chemical interaction of functional groups such as carbonyl and hydroxyl with the structure of used LDPE. Additionally, the adsorption of these functional groups on filler particles leads to an improvement in the overall properties of recycled LDPE composites [16-19].

The utilization of products obtained from recycled polyethylene reduces the need for expensive virgin polymers, lowering raw material consumption. The low cost of polymer waste and the profitability of the modification process make the development of these recycling processes highly feasible.

References

1. Abramov V.V., Chalaya N.M. Sostoyanie v proizvodstve pererabotki plastmass i vtorichnogo ikh ispol'zovaniya. *Plast. massy*, 2003, № 5, s. 4-9.
2. Korpələr doğulmadan əvvəl çirklənir. 23 dekabr 2020. <https://www.bbc.com/turkce/haberler-dunya-55412052>
3. Khattab A.A., ElZoghby A.A. Effect of recycling on the mechanical properties of low density polyethylene. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Science*, v.45, n 4, 1998, pp. 533-547.
4. Abo El-Khair M.S., Ali A.A. The mechanical behaviour of recycled high density polyethylene. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)*, Vol.3, Issue.2, March-April 2013, pp. 798-808. ISSN: 2249-6645.
5. A.S. Klinkov, P.S. Belyaev, M.V. Sokolov. *Utilizatsiya i vtorichnaya pererabotka polimernykh materialov*. Tambov: Tambovskiy gosudarstvennyy tekhnicheskij universitet, EBS ASV, 2012, 81 s. ISBN 5-8265-0424-2.

6. Ponomareva V.T., Likhacheva N.N., Tkachik Z.A. Ispol'zovanie plastmasovykh otkhodov za rubezhom. *Plasticheskie massy*, 2002, № 5, s. 44-48.
7. G.K. Lobachev, V.F. Zheltobryukhov i dr. Vtorichnye resursy: problemy, perspektivy, tekhnologiya, ekonomika. Ucheb. posobie. Volgograd, 1999, 180 s.
8. M.D. Ragushina, V.V. Bitt, E.V. Kalugina. Vliyanie razlichnykh modifikatorov na svoystva vtorichnogo polietilena, podkhody k retsiklingu. *Plasticheskie massy*, № 9-10, 2022, s. 42-45.
9. 9.A.V. Fomtsov. Novye effektivnye termostabilizatory vtorichnogo PET. *Polimernye materialy*, № 12, 2021, s. 24-25.
10. Kh. Tsveyfel, R.D. Mayer, M. Shiller. *Dobavki k polimeram. Spravochnik. SPb.: Professiya*, 2010.
11. Hagen Hanel, Akhim Rot. Obespechenie termostabil'nosti plastika v ego «vtoroy zhizni». *Polimernye materialy*, 2021, oktyabr/Kunststoff, s. 2-5.
12. B.V. Naber. Staryy plastik i more. Problemy proizvodstva, potrebleniya i retsiklinga plastmass. Chast' 2. *Polimernye materialy*, № 2, 2021, s. 30-37.
13. Yu.A. Shlyapnikov, S.G. Kiryushkin, A.P. Marin. *Antioksidantnaya stabilizatsiya polimerov. M.: Khimiya*, 1986, 256 s.
14. I.Kh. Mingalimov. Novye vozmozhnosti vtorichnoy pererabotki plastmass. *Polimernye materialy*, 2021, may, s. 38-42.
15. A.S. Klinkov, P.S. Belyaev, M.B. Sokolov. *Utilizatsiya i vtorichnaya pererabotka polimernykh materialov. Tambov: Izd-vo Tamb. gos. tekhn. un-ta*, 2005, 80 s.
16. Bilalov Ya.M., Akhmedova U.M., Alieva G.A. Povtornaya pererabotka i modifikatsiya svoystv polietilena nizkoy plotnosti, nekotorye ekonomicheskie aspekty, problemy. *Zhurnal «Khimicheskie problemy»*, 2011, № 1, s. 60-65.
17. Ahmadova Ulviyya Mobin Kyzy. Ashaghy syxlyqli polietilenin təkrar emalı prosesində mineral doldurucular və funksional qruplu birləşmələrlə modifikasiyasının tədqiqi. *Avtoreferat. Bakı*, 2014, səh. 23.
18. Ahmed H. Awad, Ramadan Elgamsy, Mohamed Hazem Abdellatif. Assessment of mechanical properties of HDPE composite with addition of marble and granite dust. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 2020, pp. 1211-1217.
19. A.H. Awad, Ahmed W. Abdel-Ghany, Ayman A. Abd El-Wahab, Ramadan El-Gamasy, Mohamed Hazem Abdellatif. The influence of adding marble and granite dust on the mechanical and physical properties of PP composites. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, Vol. 140, 2019, pp. 2615-2623.